

Supplementary material for leveraging weighted quartet distributions for enhanced species tree inference from genome-wide data

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These supplementary materials present additional results, supplementary figures, and tables.

1 Additional Results

Figure S1: **RQ1 (Experiment 1): Results on the 11-taxon dataset.** Comparison of performance when using all quartets with weights and using only the dominant quartets (with and without weights).

Figure S2: **RQ1 (Experiment 2): Results on the 11-taxon dataset.** We compare methods utilizing weighted quartets generated from BestML gene trees (GTF), bootstrap distribution of gene trees (GTF-BS), and Bayesian distribution of gene trees (GTF-MB).

Figure S3: **RQ1 (Experiment 3): Results on the 11-taxon dataset.** Performance comparison between unweighted and weighted (both exponential and reciprocal) quartets generated by SVDquartets. The unweighted quartets are amalgamated by QFM, whereas the weighted ones are processed by both wQFM and wQMC.

Figure S4: **RQ1 (Experiment 4): Results on the 11-taxon dataset.** Comparison of various BUCKy-based and ML-based methods. We also included the methods wQFM-GTF and wQMC-GTF.

Figure S5: **RQ1 (Experiment 4): Results on the 15-taxon dataset.** Comparison of various BUCKy-based and ML-based methods with wQFM-RAxML added. We also included wQFM-GTF and wQMC-GTF.

Table S1: Quartet scores of wQFM and wQMC for estimated and true gene trees in different model conditions. The highest scores have been highlighted in bold, and those closest to the true score have been italicized.

Taxa	Model Condition	Estimated Gene Trees			True Gene Trees		
		wQFM-GTF	wQMC-GTF	True Tree	wQFM-GTF	wQMC-GTF	True Tree
11	lower-ILS	<i>40412</i>	40421	40301	50737	50809	51252
	higher-ILS	<i>26680</i>	26702	26372	29268	29295	29982
15	100gene-100bp	<i>69776</i>	69930	69307	82708	82045	84634
	100gene-1000bp	<i>82129</i>	82166	82099	84437	84285	84634
	1000gene-100bp	<i>692949</i>	693656	690268	834890	827970	844184
	1000gene-1000bp	<i>817993</i>	818022	817937	843791	843362	844184
37	1X-200-50	<i>7523379</i>	7523568	7517955	11707475	11659108	11744078
	1X-200-250	<i>10568957</i>	10569443	10565291	11735692	11732415	11744078
	1X-200-500	<i>11271425</i>	11271905	11267990	11739571	11738991	11744078
	1X-200-1000	<i>11586354</i>	11586641	11584969	11743720	11743809	11744078
	0.5X-200-500	10006593	<i>10006510</i>	10003929	10311452	10310345	10311622
	2X-200-500	<i>11947020</i>	11947266	11946371	12565347	12565281	12570342
	1X-100-500	<i>5639605</i>	5640131	5636883	5871208	5870844	5874698
1X-500-500	<i>28171681</i>	28171698	28171385	29363114	29362939	29364013	

Figure S6: **RQ3: Results on the 11-taxon dataset.** We compare the best methods from previous experiments: wQFM-GTF, wQFM-GTF-MB, wQFM-SVD-Rec with ASTRAL, BUCKy, and SVDquartets. ASTRAL's weighted counterpart, configured to utilize branch supports as weights, was also analyzed. Branch supports were estimated from both non-parametric RAxML bootstrapping (wASTRAL) and Bayesian MCMC sampling (wASTRAL-MB).